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A Fuzzy Data Envelopment Analysis Approach for Measuring the Efficiency of Defense Industry Software Projects

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ABSTRACT

For centuries, defense industry projects have been of strategic importance in terms of efficient use of limited resources and achievement of high-performance targets. Such projects require a multidimensional evaluation process that encompasses not only technical capabilities but also process efficiency and resource utilisation effectiveness. Decision makers should evaluate the efficiency analysis of projects in order to optimize the resources of the projects, determine their strengths and weaknesses, and make strategic plans. However, Defense Industry projects include many factors in their processes, such as complex structures, having many inputs and outputs, resource usage, cost estimates, optional risks, and evaluation of project performance. For this reason, traditional efficiency analyses cannot model all of these uncertainties, and critical elements are overlooked in decision-making processes. In this study, Fuzzy Data Envelopment Analysis (FDEA), a more flexible and reliable method, was used for efficiency measurement of Defense Industry software projects. Since the projects are large and complex, as well as having qualitative and quantitative data, the fuzzy data envelopment method, which is a fuzzy logic version of the traditional data envelopment analysis method, was used. Within the scope of the study, the effectiveness analysis of 10 projects with 5 input criteria (“delivery time”, “process management effectiveness”, “failure frequency”, “number of project personnel”, “number of warranty period problems”) and 4 output criteria (“customer satisfaction”, “technical requirement fulfillment rate”, “warranty performance”, “revenue”) were evaluated with the FDEA method. This study aims to provide decision makers with a flexible, easy, and objective evaluation by using the FDEA method in evaluating the effectiveness analysis of defense industry projects with quantitative and qualitative data. Based on the application results, the efficiency scores for 10 software projects across companies ranged from 66% to 94% across entry and exit criteria. Among the evaluated software projects, P4 (94%), P7 (91%), and P3 (89%) had the highest efficiency scores, while P9 (66%) and P10 (68%) had the lowest. The results reveal differences in efficiency among the projects.

1 INTRODUCTION

The defense industry includes projects that involve large-scale investments and strategic decision-making processes, and that involve multiple input and output factors. The changing and evolving security dynamics and rapid developments in defense technologies over the centuries affect strategic decision-making in projects. Objective evaluation of the performance of defense industry projects, primarily due to the multidimensionality of the criteria used, the presence of complex and unclear data, and the combination of qualitative and quantitative data, makes it very difficult to evaluate project performance. Therefore, one of the methods used to evaluate the effectiveness of defense industry projects is Fuzzy DEA.

Decision makers should evaluate the efficiency analysis of projects in order to optimize the resources of the projects, determine their strengths and weaknesses and make strategic planning. In traditional DEA methods, the relative efficiency levels of projects can be evaluated based on certain inputs and outputs. In complex and multi-input and output data, the fuzzy logic method should be used. For this reason, the fuzzy logic-based FDEA method provides a more reliable evaluation of project performance even with incomplete or uncertain data and produces more objective analyses for decision makers [1]. The evaluation of defense industry projects is especially important due to their long-term processes, high costs, dynamic performance criteria, and variable operational conditions. Using a method based on mathematical models instead of intuitive and trial-and-error methods provides a more reliable evaluation of project performance [2].

The main purpose of this study is to analyze the effectiveness of defense industry projects using the FDEA method and to enable comparison of software project performances in the sector. In this direction, criteria were determined by considering the evaluations of expert opinions for the scale of project effectiveness and a data set was created. The effectiveness levels of the projects were calculated by applying the FDEA method with the evaluations of expert opinions. The application of the FDEA method provides a significant contribution to the existing literature in the evaluation and analysis of the effectiveness of defense industry projects. Within the scope of the study, studies conducted with DEA and FDEA methods in the literature, a detailed explanation of the FDEA method, and an evaluation of defense industry software projects were made.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

DEA is an efficiency analysis method developed for the purpose of measuring the relative efficiency of decision-making units (DMU) in service or production projects. In circumstances where resources are limited and outputs are multidimensional, DEA plays an important role in decision-making processes, particularly regarding project efficiency, resource utilisation, and performance management. This method is widely preferred for efficiency measurement in complex structures with a large number of inputs and outputs, such as R&D and portfolio investment projects, hospital and university service performances, and the efficiency of electricity generation plants [3]. The term DEA was first used in 1978 by Charnes, Cooper, and Rhodes, who also created the CCR model [1].

In real-life applications, it is often difficult to obtain complete and precise input and output data. The validity of traditional Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) models is contingent upon the certainty of the inputs and outputs employed. However, in cases where the data are ambiguous, open to interpretation, or described in qualitative terms, classical RIA (Ranking of Fuzzy Numbers using Index Approach) methods are inadequate. In circumstances involving such uncertainties, the utilisation of fuzzy logic-based DEA (FDEA) models is recommended. In this study, due to the scope, uncertainty level, and non-quantifiable characteristics of defence industry software projects, evaluations based on expert opinions were taken as a basis, and efficiency analysis was carried out with the FDEA method. A survey of the literature reveals a plethora of studies that have employed the DEA and FDEA methods to measure efficiency.

Ayan and Perçin (2008) studied the FDEA method was employed to comparatively measure the efficiency levels of automotive firms operating in Turkey. In the context of the automotive sector,

characterised by intense competition and volatile market conditions, the input-oriented Fuzzy CCR model was selected for its capacity to analyse uncertain data. In the present study, the data of 10 different companies for the period between 2010 and 2014 were evaluated. The number of employees, total assets, total production volume, and total costs were taken as input variables, while net sales and total exports were taken as output variables. The application of the model resulted in the calculation of relative efficiency scores for the firms on an annual basis. These scores were then used to analyse performance differences based on the same annual periods [4]. Ji and Lee (2010), in their study, aimed to measure the efficiency levels of the number of employees and store area as input criteria and sales volume and profit as output criteria. In another example, input: resources used; output: production quantity and output criteria by using the DEA method for store performance [2].

Tavana, Khalili-Damghani, and Sadi-Nezhad (2013) developed a novel fuzzy DEA model that simultaneously addresses uncertainty and fuzziness in NASA's high technology project selection process. In the course of the study, a total of 20 projects were evaluated on the basis of total cost and production time (inputs); safety, reliability, feasibility, and reusability (outputs). The opinions of five decision makers were expressed in trapezoidal fuzzy numbers and linguistic terms and combined with the geometric mean. The model integrating α -level sets and a probabilistic approach has the advantage of lower computational complexity and eliminates the need for defuzzification compared to classical fuzzy DEA. The application demonstrates that the proposed model is an effective and systematic evaluation tool in multi-criteria, multi-decision maker, and uncertain environments [5].

Yavuz (2013) analysed the financial performances of eight large state-owned banks operating in Turkey for the period 2017-2021 with the FDEA method in order to evaluate the variable and uncertain conditions more realistically. The data utilised in the study were compiled from publicly available annual reports, with the number of personnel, number of branches, and total assets serving as the input criteria, and total loans, total deposits, and net profit serving as the output criteria. Following a thorough analysis, efficiency scores were calculated for each bank over the years, and their efficiency in the sector was compared [6]. Trindade, Barroso, and Machado (2015) applied the input-oriented BCC DEA model to evaluate the efficiency of projects in a Portuguese electricity distribution company. They determined the input and output criteria as the average investment cost and duration per project; safety, environmental impact, public impact, system outage, and revenue [7].

Türkşen (2018) study applied the FDEA method with data from 2015 to measure the effectiveness levels of public universities in Türkiye in the field of education and training. In the study, data were collected from three institutions: the Council of Higher Education (YÖK), the Turkish Statistical Institute (TÜİK), and the Ministry of Development. The number of faculty members, the number of students, the investment budget, and current expenditures were taken as input criteria, and the number of graduates, the number of academic publications, and the number of TUBITAK-supported projects were taken as output criteria [8]. Toloo and Mirbolouki (2019) developed a new DEA-based project selection methodology that considers limited resources in the selection of information systems projects. The input criteria used in the model are software, training, and support costs, while the output criteria are defined as time saving and improvement of management capabilities [9].

Uyaroğlu (2022) studied, aimed to compare the annual efficiency of five defence industry companies operating in the defence industry between 2012 and 2021. These companies are published annually by the Defence and Aerospace Industry Manufacturers Association (SASAD), and Uyaroğlu applied the FDEA method in his analysis. In the study, the number of imports and the amount spent on R&D are used as independent variables, while the number of exports and turnover values are used as dependent variables. The application of the FDEA model enabled the calculation of efficiency scores at both the level of years and firms. In addition, the analysis revealed change trends in the sector and the most efficient years [10]. Sueyoshi and Ryu (2022) developed a two-stage DEA model with time lag for the purpose of evaluating the technology transition (spin-in) performance of 252 small firms with at least 15 patent applications under the US Department of Defense's SBIR program.

In the initial phase, designated as the SBIR (Small Business Innovation Research) funding stage, the number of employees and the technological distance to the DoD (Department of Defense) are considered as inputs. Conversely, the number of patents and network centrality are regarded as outputs. In the second stage, these outputs were used as new entries, and the federal contract amount was considered the final output. The study under discussion highlights the impact of social capital indicators on technology transition success and demonstrates that RIA is an effective tool for the evaluation of small firms in the defense sector [11].

Wang, Liu, and Zhang (2022) developed a new three-stage DEA model to evaluate the effectiveness of 55 public building energy efficiency renovation projects (BERPs) implemented in Beijing between 2014 and 2018. In the project, they determined the input criteria as project capital, construction period, and dynamic payback period, and the output criteria as renovated area and estimated annual energy savings [12].

Örkçü and Sevim (2023) employed both classical and advanced DEA models for the purpose of evaluating the efficiency levels of firms operating within METU Technopolis and identifying the most efficient firm. The input variables are defined as the number of R&D personnel and R&D expenses; the output variables are defined as the number of projects, intellectual property rights, R&D income, number of collaborations, firm score, and number of supported projects. In accordance with the data collected in 2018, a total of 23 firms, each with R&D revenues of more than 3 million TL, were the subject of evaluation. In this evaluation, the super efficiency, Wang & Jiang, Toloo, Wang & Chin (neutral cross-efficiency), and Toloo & Salahi models were applied in addition to the CCR model. In all models, the F18 unit is distinguished as the most efficient, while the Toloo and Salahi models are the most distinctive in terms of ranking power, as they assign a score greater than 1 to only one firm. Consequently, they assert that they have developed a DEA model that is distinct from other studies. The study demonstrates that a range of DEA models can make a strategic contribution to the measurement of efficiency in the comparative performance analysis of technopark firms [13].

Chenrrim and Relvas (2025) applied the BCC (VRS) DEA and Global Malmquist Productivity Index models to time series data on three railway freight companies (Medway, Captrain Portugal, and Renfe Mercancías) in order to evaluate the impact of high-speed lines on freight transport in Portuguese railway transport. The inputs employed in the study comprised the number of employees (persons), the length of the railway network (kilometres), the number of freight wagons (units), and the maximum permitted speed (kilometres per hour). The train-kilometre (train/km) was utilised as the output variable. It has been demonstrated that the efficiency of freight transport on high-speed rail networks is not significantly enhanced by increasing the speed of operation. The primary factors contributing to efficiency enhancement are found in the optimisation of personnel and wagons [14].

3 METHOD

The DEA model was developed by Charnes, Cooper, and Rhodes for the evaluation of relative efficiency levels in decision-making units (DMU) projects [15]. In projects with multiple inputs and outputs, the Fuzzy DEA model is used because DMUs encounter complex and qualitative-quantitative data. In cases where data is uncertain and incomplete, and subjective evaluations are common, FDEA has a more flexible usage structure and objective analyses [16;17].

In this study, the FDEA method is used to evaluate the efficiency levels of DMU. FDEA includes a systematic approach by considering the uncertainty in the data and expert opinions. In this way, the integration of the traditional DEA model with fuzzy logic guides decision makers in making objective decisions.

One of the main advantages of FDEA is that it can be worked with more flexible and easily obtained data compared to alternative methods, and the results can be compared between units. In this way, it is widely preferred in project performance evaluation studies [17]. FDEA is used to measure efficiency and compare results, especially in complex structures where resources are limited and there are multiple inputs and outputs.

In this study, the FDEA model developed by Liu and Liu was employed, as it is one of the fuzzy set methods. Defence industry software projects are characterised by complex and uncertain data, which makes it difficult to interpret project effectiveness.

Consequently, it has become a widely used method in the literature for assessing the efficiency of DMUs. One of the main advantages of FDEA is that it can be worked with more flexible and easily obtained data compared to alternative methods, and the results can be compared between units. In this way, it is widely preferred in project performance evaluation studies [17]. FDEA is used to measure efficiency and compare results, especially in complex structures where resources are limited and there are multiple inputs and outputs.

In this method, efficient units receive a score of 1, while inefficient units receive scores less than 1. The difference in efficiency scores between efficient and inefficient units reflects the potential to achieve the same level of outputs with fewer inputs [18].

Charnes, Cooper, and Rhodes introduced the CCR model in 1978, which is one of the foundational DEA models and assumes constant returns to scale. The CCR model is used to measure the technical efficiency of decision-making units (DMUs) [15]. This model can be analysed in two main orientations: input-oriented and output-oriented. In the output-oriented CCR model, input values for each DMU are held constant while seeking to maximize output levels to the most efficient scale [17]. Therefore, the output-oriented CCR model is adopted in this study.

The mathematical formulation of the FDEA model is presented in Equations (1)– (6) [17], and the implementation steps of FDEA are shown in Figure 1.

$$\text{Max } Z_j = \left(\frac{1}{4}\right) * \left(\sum_{r=1}^s \mu_r^l y_{rj}^l + 2 \sum_{r=1}^s \mu_r^m y_{rj}^m + \sum_{r=1}^s \mu_r^u y_{rj}^u\right) \quad (1)$$

Subject to

$$\left(\frac{1}{4}\right) * \left(\sum_{r=1}^s \gamma_r^l x_{rj}^l + 2 \sum_{r=1}^s \gamma_r^m x_{rj}^m + \sum_{r=1}^s \gamma_r^u x_{rj}^u\right) = 1 \quad (2)$$

$$\left(\frac{1}{4}\right) * \left(\sum_{r=1}^s \mu_r^l y_{rj}^l + 2 \sum_{r=1}^s \mu_r^m y_{rj}^m + \sum_{r=1}^s \mu_r^u y_{rj}^u\right) - \left(\frac{1}{4}\right) * \left(\sum_{r=1}^s \gamma_r^l x_{rj}^l + 2 \sum_{r=1}^s \gamma_r^m x_{rj}^m + \sum_{r=1}^s \gamma_r^u x_{rj}^u\right) \leq 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\gamma_r^l ; x_{rj}^l ; \gamma_r^m ; x_{rj}^m ; \gamma_r^u ; x_{rj}^u ; \mu_r^l ; \mu_r^m ; \mu_r^u ; y_{rj}^l ; y_{rj}^m ; y_{rj}^u \geq 0 ; r = 1, \dots, s ; i = 1, \dots, m \quad (4)$$

$\gamma_r^l ; \gamma_r^m ; \gamma_r^u$: weights assigned to fuzzy input values

$x_{rj}^l ; x_{rj}^m ; x_{rj}^u$: fuzzy input values (lower, modal, upper) for input i DMU j

$\mu_r^l ; \mu_r^m ; \mu_r^u$: weights assigned to fuzzy output values

$y_{rj}^l ; y_{rj}^m ; y_{rj}^u$: fuzzy output values (lower, modal, upper) for output r DMU j (5)

s : number of outputs, m : number of inputs (6)

Figure 1: The implementation steps of FDEA

4 CASE STUDY

A review of extant literature reveals a plethora of studies addressing the performance measurement of a wide range of entities, including electricity distribution, university efficiency, health services, the economic efficiency of nations, R&D projects, portfolio selection, and the evaluation of airport infrastructures. In the context of projects characterised by intricate structures, such as the defense industry, where strategic and multi-criteria decisions are made and the added value of the projects is high, the measurement of effectiveness and efficiency assumes significant importance. Given the significance of effective resource utilisation in such projects, and the numerous factors it affects, it is imperative to measure efficiency values and implement improvements.

In real-life problems, the FDEA model is needed because the data are complex, ambiguous, and qualitative, and expert opinions are often prioritized. This study aims to objectively analyse the outputs of the projects in return for the use of resources and to determine their efficiency levels. When the defense industry projects are examined, the output-oriented CCR method was used as the FDEA model presented in Liu and Liu's study in 2002 due to the complexity and long duration of the projects as well as the need for expert opinions.

In the application, a total of nine criteria were employed. These criteria were determined and evaluated based on literature reviews and the opinions of three experts with 5-20 years of experience working in a defense industry company. The identified criteria are as follows: Project delivery time (in months) (X1), process efficiency (%) (X2), human resource utilisation (in person-months) (X3), warranty period problems (in terms of the problematic period) (X4) were defined as inputs, and warranty satisfaction value (on a 1-5 scale) (Y1), warranty performance (Y2), technical requirement fulfilment rate (%) (Y3), defect frequency (in units) (Y4), revenue (in million USD) (Y5) were defined as outputs. Each project was treated as a decision unit (DMU), and the efficiency scores were calculated through linear programming models built on Excel Solver add-in. The description of the criteria are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Description of Criteria

Criterion Name	Description
X1	The total time between the start and finish of the project.
X2	The effort expended throughout the project process (resource planning, workflow, communication and coordination, etc.) represents the overall efficiency.
X3	It is the total labour force of the engineers assigned throughout the project, calculated in person-months.
X4	These are problems evaluated by considering the frequency, severity, and resolution time of malfunctions experienced during the warranty period.
Y1	It is the satisfaction score derived from feedback received from customers during the warranty period.
Y2	It represents the continuity of system performance (malfunctions, system activity, etc.) during the warranty period.
Y3	It represents the rate at which technical requirements requested during the project were met.
Y4	It shows the total number of errors detected in the developed system throughout the project.
Y5	It is the total revenue level obtained upon completion of the project.

Projects with efficiency scores of 1 are categorised as 'fully efficient', while those with efficiency scores below 1 are categorised as 'relatively inefficient'. During the solution process, the objective function and constraints were defined in a distinct manner for each project. The results obtained are shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Efficiency Scores of Projects

Project (P)	Efficiency Scores (%)
P1	69%
P2	70%
P3	89%
P4	94%
P5	70%
P6	72%
P7	91%
P8	70%
P9	66%
P10	68%

To evaluate the data sensitivity analysis of the model, the outputs of the first three projects P1, P2 and P3 were halved, and the efficiency scores changed to P1: 34%, P2: 35%, and P3: 46%. Thus, the stability and robustness of the model were demonstrated in the case study. The fact that DEA-based

efficiency measurement studies on the defense industry are limited in the literature makes this study research that fills an important gap in terms of both methodological approach and application area. This study aims to provide strategic guidance to decision makers. It also aims to encourage decision makers to adopt a more systematic approach by considering project efficiency values instead of evaluating large, complex projects with quantitative and qualitative data using heuristic or trial-and-error methods.

5 CONCLUSION

The existing literature indicates that efficiency measurement has been widely utilized across a range of sectors, including electricity distribution, university performance, healthcare services, national economic productivity, R&D projects, portfolio selection, and airport infrastructure evaluation. Efficiency analysis plays a critical role in strategic, multi-criteria, and resource-intensive projects such as those in the defense industry. In such projects, resource efficiency is not only linked to output but also to multidimensional performance indicators such as time, cost, human resources, and customer satisfaction. Therefore, objectively measuring efficiency levels provides decision-makers with valuable strategic insights.

In this study, the output-oriented CCR model, one of the FDEA (Fuzzy Data Envelopment Analysis) methods, was applied to analyse the efficiency of outputs relative to resources used in defense industry software projects. The scope of the study, ten projects selected among defense industry software projects, was evaluated on four input and five output criteria, and their effectiveness was measured. Input criteria included project duration, process efficiency, human resource utilization, and issues encountered during the warranty period. Output criteria consisted of warranty satisfaction, warranty performance, technical requirement fulfilment rate, failure frequency, and project revenue. Each project was treated as a decision-making unit (DMU), and linear programming solutions were performed using the Excel Solver.

The project efficiency values obtained as a result of the analysis are presented in Table 2. When Table 2 is examined, it is observed that only two of the ten projects have efficiency values of 90% and above, while the efficiency values of the other projects are low and close to each other. Defense industry projects have a very complex structure and qualitative data due to their large scale and long duration, as well as being software projects. In this context, it has been determined that expert opinions in project planning are generally evaluated intuitively, and strategic project planning and evaluation are carried out by trial-and-error methods or by focusing only on project outputs.

As a result, it is concluded that such complex and large projects need to be evaluated with more robust analysis methods. Of the ten projects analysed, P1, P9, and P10 exhibited the lowest efficiency scores and showed a significant performance gap compared to other projects. This suggests that these projects are in urgent need of corrective action. In particular, it is important to focus on the input criteria of these projects and revise the input criteria in similar projects. Through this strategy, it will be possible to increase project efficiency by achieving maximum output with minimum inputs.

By systematically identifying the specific output factors in which inefficient projects exhibit underperformance (such as increased technical risks, inaccurate forecasting, or inadequate fulfilment of customer requirements), it becomes possible to develop and implement targeted improvement strategies. These strategies should be designed to address both managerial and operational dimensions. In this regard, enhancing the quality and effectiveness of technical deliverables, optimizing the use of available resources, and strengthening project management practices emerge as critical areas for intervention to improve overall project efficiency.

The fact that most projects were evaluated as efficient indicates that resources were generally used effectively within the decision-making environment where the model was applied. Nonetheless, the findings also highlight opportunities for sustainable improvement among the inefficient projects. FDEA not only enables the assessment of efficiency but also serves as a powerful decision-support tool by identifying areas requiring development.

In this regard, the study provides a significant contribution by addressing the need for objective and systematic evaluation in both defense industry projects and multi-criteria decision-making environments more broadly.

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